

Standard Model at High Temperatures

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The article presents a new realization of the hypothesis about the simplification of the gauge group of the Standard Model with increasing the temperature of the Universe, i.e. when moving back in time to the moment of its occurrence. It is assumed that this simplification is achieved by the gauge group contraction with the parameter, that decreases with increasing temperature. The Lagrangian of the Standard Model is divided into terms that differ in powers of the contraction parameter. This makes it possible to arrange in time the stages of development of the Standard Model as the Universe cools. The evolution of the properties of particles and their interactions is based on the explicit form of the intermediate Lagrangians and occurs in a natural order from simpler to more complicated structures, starting from the Planck scale 10^{19} GeV. The contraction hypothesis of the gauge group of the Standard Model does not contradict LHC experimental data on the Higgs boson production cross sections.

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1. Introduction

Today the Standard Model is the only theory of elementary particles and their interactions. It includes the Electroweak Model and Quantum Chromodynamics (QCD). The theory describes the experimental data well. The discovery of the Higgs boson in LHC experiments has convincingly confirmed the correctness of the theory. If we are interested in particle properties at very high energies and want to remain on a scientific basis, we need to use this theory at high temperatures. Despite the presence in the theory of a large number of free parameters [1], there is no parameter among them, associated with the temperature of the Universe and regulating the order of energies at which the standard model adequately describes the world of elementary particles and their interactions.

Grand Unified Theories (GUTs) are the high-energy completions of the Standard Model in the last half century. According to GUTs at high energies, the electromagnetic, weak, and

strong interactions are combine into a single force. Historically, the first GUT based on the simple Lie group $SU(5)$ was proposed in 1974 [2, 3]. Despite the abundance of impressive theoretical developments, the predictions of GUTs have not been experimentally confirmed [4].

The Standard Model is a gauge theory based on a gauge group $SU(3) \times SU(2) \times U(1)$. QCD with the $SU(3)$ gauge group describes quarks and their strong interactions. Its characteristic temperature is about of 0.2 GeV. The Electroweak Model combines weak and electromagnetic interactions and is the gauge theory with the $SU(2) \times U(1)$ gauge group. The group $SU(2)$ is charged with the weak interactions at the characteristic temperature 100 GeV, whereas $U(1)$ is connected with the long-range electromagnetic interactions. Because of zero mass photon its characteristic temperature extends up to “infinite” Planck energy 10^{19} GeV, i.e. up to the limit where gravitational interactions become significant. Based on the observation of the characteristic energies, [5–7] proposed a new conjecture: **the Standard Model gauge group becomes simpler with**

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increasing temperature of the Universe.

In other words, as the Universe cools down, the microcosm naturally evolves from simple structures to more complex ones. **The operation of group contraction is proposed as a mechanism for changing the gauge group.** Since the average energy (temperature T) of a hot Universe is related to its age [8], we choose the contraction parameter in the form $\epsilon = \left(\frac{A}{T}\right)^q$, $q > 0$, so that it tends to zero as the temperature rises to infinity as it approaches the moment of its creation as a result of the Big Bang. Here A is a constant of dimension T .

Group contraction [9] is well known in physics. A simple group transforms into a nonsemisimple one under contraction. The notion of contraction was extended to algebraic structures as well [10]. Under contraction of the symmetry group of a physical system, it goes over to some limit state. We will discuss the modified Standard Model with the contracted gauge group.

Based on current knowledge of the world of particles we get the limit of the Standard Model which corresponds to very high temperatures. This limit is generated by the contraction of the gauge groups $SU(2)$ and $SU(3)$ [7]. Similar “infinitely” high temperatures could exist in the early Universe [8]. The Standard Model Lagrangian splits into a number of terms with different degrees of the contraction parameter $\epsilon \rightarrow 0$. As far as the average energy in the hot Universe is connected with its age, then moving forward in time, i.e. back to the high-temperature contraction, we conclude that the particles pass through a number of stages in their evolution from the “infinite” temperature state to the Standard Model state. These stages of reconstruction of electroweak and color symmetries differ in the powers of the contraction parameter and consequently by the time of its creation. The Standard Model contraction makes it possible to distinguish these stages as “earlier-later”, but does not allow to determine the time that passed after the creation of the Universe. Additional assumptions are required to estimate the absolute time.

Since the change in the gauge group during contraction occurs continuously, one can try to catch the influence of the contraction effect by comparing the data obtained at the LHC on the cross section for the production of the Higgs boson at different energies with the theoretical dependence of the cross section on the temperature of the Universe. Analysis of the dominant mechanism for the production and detection of Higgs bosons at the LHC in a four-lepton process in terms of temperature dependence of the corresponding Feynman diagram leads to the conclusion that the hypothesis about the contraction of the gauge group of the standard model at least does not contradict the experimental data on the cross sections for the production of Higgs bosons [11].

2. Electroweak model at high energies

The Electroweak Model is the gauge theory with the $SU(2) \times U(1)$ gauge group. We will introduce a contracted group $SU(2; \epsilon)$ and corresponding space $\mathbf{C}_2(\epsilon)$ by the consistent rescaling of the group $SU(2)$ and the space \mathbf{C}_2

$$\begin{pmatrix} z'_1 \\ \epsilon z'_2 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} \alpha & \epsilon\beta \\ -\epsilon\bar{\beta} & \bar{\alpha} \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} z_1 \\ \epsilon z_2 \end{pmatrix},$$

$$\det u(\epsilon) = |\alpha|^2 + \epsilon^2|\beta|^2 = 1, \quad u(\epsilon)u^\dagger(\epsilon) = 1. \quad (2.1)$$

Here ϵ denotes the contraction parameter: $\epsilon \rightarrow 0$. Under this limit, the form

$$z^\dagger(\epsilon)z(\epsilon) = |z_1|^2 + \epsilon^2|z_2|^2 \quad (2.2)$$

is invariant.

The contracted group $SU(2; \epsilon = 0)$ is isomorphic to Euclid group $E(2)$. The contracted space $\mathbf{C}_2(\epsilon = 0)$ is splitted on the base spanned by the $\{z_1\}$ coordinate and the fiber spanned by the $\{z_2\}$ coordinate. (The non-relativistic space-time is the best known example of a fiber space. Its time axis represents the one-dimensional base and its three-dimensional space is interpreted as

fiber.) The unitary group $U(1)$ and its action in the space $\mathbf{C}_2(\epsilon = 0)$ do not change and are given by $\vec{z}' = e^{i\omega/2}\vec{z} = e^{i\omega Y}\vec{z}$, $\omega \in \mathbf{R}$.

The space $\mathbf{C}_2(\epsilon)$ can be obtained from \mathbf{C}_2 by substitution of z_2 by ϵz_2 . The substitution $\beta \rightarrow \epsilon\beta$ induces the other ones for Lie algebra generators $T_1 \rightarrow \epsilon T_1, T_2 \rightarrow \epsilon T_2, T_3 \rightarrow T_3$. These new generators obey the commutation relations

$$[T_1, T_2] = i\epsilon^2 T_3, \quad [T_3, T_1] = iT_2, \quad [T_2, T_3] = iT_1 \tag{2.3}$$

and form Lie algebra $su(2; \epsilon)$. The algebra $su(2; \epsilon = 0)$ structure is a semi-direct sum of commutative subalgebra $t_2 = \{T_1, T_2\}$ and subalgebra $u(1) = \{T_3\}$, namely $su(2; \epsilon) = t_2 \ltimes u(1)$.

Instead of transforming the generators we can transform the gauge fields

$$A_\mu(x) = -ig \sum_{k=1}^3 T_k A_\mu^k(x), \quad B_\mu(x) = -ig' B_\mu(x), \tag{2.4}$$

where g and g' are the constants, as follows

$$A_\mu^1 \rightarrow \epsilon A_\mu^1, \quad A_\mu^2 \rightarrow \epsilon A_\mu^2, \quad A_\mu^3 \rightarrow A_\mu^3, \quad B_\mu \rightarrow B_\mu. \tag{2.5}$$

The substitution $\beta \rightarrow \epsilon\beta$ induces multiplication of the standard gauge fields

$$Z_\mu = \frac{1}{\sqrt{g^2 + g'^2}} (gA_\mu^3 - g'B_\mu),$$

$$A_\mu = \frac{1}{\sqrt{g^2 + g'^2}} (g'A_\mu^3 + gB_\mu),$$

$$W_\mu^\pm = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} (A_\mu^1 \mp iA_\mu^2) \tag{2.6}$$

in the form

$$W_\mu^\pm \rightarrow \epsilon W_\mu^\pm, \quad Z_\mu \rightarrow Z_\mu, \quad A_\mu \rightarrow A_\mu. \tag{2.7}$$

The boson sector $L_B = L_A + L_\phi$ includes the Lagrangian of the gauge fields

$$L_A = -\frac{1}{4}[(F_{\mu\nu}^1)^2 + (F_{\mu\nu}^2)^2 + (F_{\mu\nu}^3)^2] - \frac{1}{4}(B_{\mu\nu})^2,$$

$$F_{\mu\nu} = \partial_\mu A_\nu - \partial_\nu A_\mu + [A_\mu, A_\nu],$$

$$B_{\mu\nu} = \partial_\mu B_\nu - \partial_\nu B_\mu \tag{2.8}$$

and the Lagrangian of the matter fields

$$L_\phi = \frac{1}{2}(D_\mu\phi)^\dagger D_\mu\phi - \frac{\lambda}{4}(\phi^\dagger\phi - v^2)^2,$$

$$\phi = \begin{pmatrix} \phi_1 \\ \phi_2 \end{pmatrix} \in \mathbf{C}_2. \tag{2.9}$$

The covariant derivatives are given by

$$D_\mu\phi = \partial_\mu\phi - ig \left(\sum_{k=1}^3 T_k A_\mu^k \right) \phi - ig' Y B_\mu\phi, \tag{2.10}$$

where $T_k = \frac{1}{2}\tau_k$, $k = 1, 2, 3$ are the $SU(2)$ generators, $Y = \frac{1}{2}\mathbf{1}$ is the $U(1)$ generator, τ_k are the Pauli matrices. The mechanism of spontaneous symmetry breaking generates masses of vector bosons. One of L_B ground states

$$\phi^{vac} = \begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ v \end{pmatrix}, \quad A_\mu^k = B_\mu = 0 \tag{2.11}$$

is taken as a vacuum state of the model, and small field excitations $v + \chi(x)$ with respect to this vacuum are regarded. In this case, the field of the Higgs boson χ , the constant v , and also the particle masses depending on v are not multiplied by the contraction parameter.

As a result of field transformations (2.7) bosonic Lagrangian of the contracted electroweak model can be written in the form

$$L_B(\epsilon) = L_{B,0} + \epsilon^2 L_{B,2} + L_{B,0}^{int} + \epsilon^2 L_{B,2}^{int} + \epsilon^4 L_{B,4}^{int}, \tag{2.12}$$

where

$$L_{B,0} = -\frac{1}{4}\mathcal{F}_{\mu\nu}^2 - \frac{1}{4}\mathcal{Z}_{\mu\nu}^2 + \frac{1}{2}m_Z^2(Z_\mu)^2$$

$$+ \frac{1}{2}(\partial_\mu\chi)^2 - \frac{1}{2}m_\chi^2\chi^2, \tag{2.13}$$

$$L_{B,2} = -\frac{1}{2}\mathcal{W}_{\mu\nu}^+\mathcal{W}_{\mu\nu}^- + m_W^2 W_\mu^+ W_\mu^-, \tag{2.14}$$

$$L_{B,0}^{int} = -\frac{\lambda}{4}\chi^4 - \lambda v\chi^3 + \frac{gm_z}{2\cos\theta_W}\chi(Z_\mu)^2 + \frac{g^2}{8\cos^2\theta_W}\chi^2(Z_\mu)^2, \quad (2.15)$$

$$\begin{aligned} L_{B,2}^{int} = & g\chi W_\mu^+ W_\mu^- + \frac{g^2}{4}\chi^2 W_\mu^+ W_\nu^- - 2ig(W_\mu^+ W_\nu^- - W_\mu^- W_\nu^+) (\mathcal{F}_{\mu\nu} \sin\theta_W + \mathcal{Z}_{\mu\nu} \cos\theta_W) \\ & - \frac{i}{2}e [A_\mu (\mathcal{W}_{\mu\nu}^+ W_\nu^- - \mathcal{W}_{\mu\nu}^- W_\nu^+) - A_\nu (\mathcal{W}_{\mu\nu}^+ W_\mu^- - \mathcal{W}_{\mu\nu}^- W_\mu^+)] \\ & - \frac{i}{2}g \cos\theta_W [Z_\mu (\mathcal{W}_{\mu\nu}^+ W_\nu^- - \mathcal{W}_{\mu\nu}^- W_\nu^+) - Z_\nu (\mathcal{W}_{\mu\nu}^+ W_\mu^- - \mathcal{W}_{\mu\nu}^- W_\mu^+)] \\ & - \frac{e^2}{4} \left\{ [(W_\mu^+)^2 + (W_\mu^-)^2] (A_\nu)^2 - 2(W_\mu^+ W_\nu^+ + W_\mu^- W_\nu^-) A_\mu A_\nu \right. \\ & \left. + [(W_\nu^+)^2 + (W_\nu^-)^2] (A_\mu)^2 \right\} - \frac{g^2}{4} \cos\theta_W \left\{ [(W_\mu^+)^2 + (W_\mu^-)^2] (Z_\nu)^2 \right. \\ & \left. - 2(W_\mu^+ W_\nu^+ + W_\mu^- W_\nu^-) Z_\mu Z_\nu + [(W_\nu^+)^2 + (W_\nu^-)^2] (Z_\mu)^2 \right\} \\ & - eg \cos\theta_W \left[W_\mu^+ W_\mu^- A_\nu Z_\nu + W_\nu^+ W_\nu^- A_\mu Z_\mu - \frac{1}{2} (W_\mu^+ W_\nu^- + W_\nu^+ W_\mu^-) (A_\mu Z_\nu + A_\nu Z_\mu) \right], \quad (2.16) \end{aligned}$$

$$L_{B,4}^{int} = \frac{g^2}{4} (W_\mu^+ W_\nu^- - W_\mu^- W_\nu^+)^2. \quad (2.17)$$

The fermion sector is represented by the lepton L_L and quark L_Q Lagrangians. For particles of the first-generation, the lepton Lagrangian is written in the form

$$\begin{aligned} L_{L,e} = & L_l^\dagger i\tilde{\tau}_\mu D_\mu L_l + e_r^\dagger i\tau_\mu D_\mu e_r \\ & - h_e [e_r^\dagger (\phi^\dagger L_l) + (L_l^\dagger \phi) e_r], \quad (2.18) \end{aligned}$$

where $L_l = \begin{pmatrix} \nu_l \\ e_l \end{pmatrix} \in \mathbf{C}_2$ is the $SU(2)$ doublet,

e_r is the $SU(2)$ singlet, $\tau_0 = \tilde{\tau}_0 = \mathbf{1}$, $\tilde{\tau}_k = -\tau_k$, h_e is the constant, e_r, e_l, ν_l are the two-component Lorentz spinors, and D_μ are the covariant derivatives

$$\begin{aligned} D_\mu L_l = & \partial_\mu L_l - i\frac{g}{\sqrt{2}} (W_\mu^+ T_+ + W_\mu^- T_-) L_l \\ & - i\frac{g}{\cos\theta_w} Z_\mu (T_3 - Q \sin^2\theta_w) L_l - ie A_\mu Q L_l, \end{aligned}$$

$$D_\mu e_r = \partial_\mu e_r - ig' Q A_\mu e_r \cos\theta_w + ig' Q Z_\mu e_r \sin\theta_w, \quad (2.19)$$

where $T_{\pm} = T_1 \pm iT_2$, $Q = Y + T_3$ is the generator of the $U(1)_{em}$ electromagnetic subgroup, $Y = \frac{1}{2}\mathbf{1}$ is the hypercharge, $e = gg'(g^2 + g'^2)^{-\frac{1}{2}}$ is the electron charge, and $\sin\theta_w = eg^{-1}$.

The components of the lepton fields $L_l = \begin{pmatrix} \nu_l \\ e_l \end{pmatrix}$ are transformed as the components of the vector z , namely:

$$e_l \rightarrow \epsilon e_l, \quad e_r \rightarrow \epsilon e_r, \quad \nu_l \rightarrow \nu_l. \quad (2.20)$$

As a result of transformations (2.7),(2.20) the lepton Lagrangian (2.18) takes the following form:

$$L_L(\epsilon) = L_{L,0} + L_{L,0}^{int} + \epsilon^2(L_{L,2} + L_{L,2}^{int}), \quad (2.21)$$

$$L_{L,0} = \nu_l^\dagger i\tilde{\tau}_\mu \partial_\mu \nu_l, \quad (2.22)$$

$$L_{L,0}^{int} = e\nu_l^\dagger \tilde{\tau}_\mu A_\mu \nu_l + \frac{g \cos 2\theta_w}{2 \cos \theta_w} \nu_l^\dagger \tilde{\tau}_\mu Z_\mu \nu_l, \quad (2.23)$$

$$L_{L,2} = e_l^\dagger i\tilde{\tau}_\mu \partial_\mu e_l + e_r^\dagger i\tilde{\tau}_\mu \partial_\mu e_r$$

$$-m_e(e_l^\dagger e_l + e_r^\dagger e_r) - h_e \chi(e_l^\dagger e_l + e_r^\dagger e_r), \quad (2.24)$$

$$\begin{aligned} L_{L,2}^{int} = & -\frac{g}{2 \cos \theta_w} e_l^\dagger \tilde{\tau}_\mu Z_\mu e_l + g' \cos \theta_w e_r^\dagger \tilde{\tau}_\mu A_\mu e_r - g' \sin \theta_w e_r^\dagger \tilde{\tau}_\mu Z_\mu e_r \\ & + \frac{g}{\sqrt{2}} \left(\nu_l^\dagger \tilde{\tau}_\mu W_\mu^+ e_l + e_l^\dagger \tilde{\tau}_\mu W_\mu^- \nu_l \right). \end{aligned} \quad (2.25)$$

The quark Lagrangian is constructed in a similar way:

$$\begin{aligned} L_Q = & Q_l^\dagger i\tilde{\tau}_\mu D_\mu Q_l + u_r^\dagger i\tau_\mu D_\mu u_r + d_r^\dagger i\tau_\mu D_\mu d_r \\ & -h_d[d_r^\dagger(\phi^\dagger Q_l) + (Q_l^\dagger \phi)d_r] - h_u[u_r^\dagger(\tilde{\phi}^\dagger Q_l) + (Q_l^\dagger \tilde{\phi})u_r], \end{aligned} \quad (2.26)$$

where the left quark fields make up the $SU(2)$ doublet $Q_l = \begin{pmatrix} u_l \\ d_l \end{pmatrix}$, the right fields u_r, d_r are $SU(2)$ singlets, $\tilde{\phi}_i = \epsilon_{ik}\bar{\phi}_k$, $\epsilon_{00} = 1$, $\epsilon_{ii} = -1$ make up a conjugate representation of the $SU(2)$ group, h_u, h_d are the constants. All fields u_l, d_l, u_r, d_r are two-component Lorentz spinors. The covariant derivatives are

$$D_\mu Q_l = \left(\partial_\mu - ig \sum_{k=1}^3 \frac{\tau_k}{2} A_\mu^k - ig' \frac{1}{6} B_\mu \right) Q_l,$$

$$D_\mu u_r = \left(\partial_\mu - ig' \frac{2}{3} B_\mu \right) u_r,$$

$$D_\mu d_r = \left(\partial_\mu + ig' \frac{1}{3} B_\mu \right) d_r. \quad (2.27)$$

After substitution $d_l \rightarrow \epsilon d_l$, $d_r \rightarrow \epsilon d_r$ the quark Lagrangian (2.26) in terms of u and d quarks fields can be written as

$$L_Q(\epsilon) = L_{Q,0} + \epsilon^2 L_{Q,2} + L_{Q,0}^{int} + \epsilon^2 L_{Q,2}^{int}, \quad (2.28)$$

where

$$L_{Q,0} = u_l^\dagger i\tilde{\tau}_\mu \partial_\mu u_l + u_r^\dagger i\tau_\mu \partial_\mu u_r$$

$$-m_u(u_r^\dagger u_l + u_l^\dagger u_r) - h_u \chi(u_r^\dagger u_l + u_l^\dagger u_r), \quad (2.29)$$

$$L_{Q,0}^{int} = \frac{2e}{3} u_l^\dagger \tilde{\tau}_\mu A_\mu u_l$$

$$+ \left(\frac{g}{2} \cos \theta_w - \frac{g'}{6} \sin \theta_w \right) u_l^\dagger \tilde{\tau}_\mu Z_\mu u_l$$

$$+\frac{2}{3}g' \cos \theta_w u_r^\dagger \tau_\mu A_\mu u_r - \frac{2}{3}g' \sin \theta_w u_r^\dagger \tau_\mu Z_\mu u_r, \quad -m_d(d_r^\dagger d_l + d_l^\dagger d_r) - h_d \chi(d_r^\dagger d_l + d_l^\dagger d_r), \quad (2.31)$$

$$(2.30)$$

$$L_{Q,2} = d_l^\dagger i \tilde{\tau}_\mu \partial_\mu d_l + d_r^\dagger i \tau_\mu \partial_\mu d_r$$

$$L_{Q,2}^{int} = - \left(\frac{g}{2} \cos \theta_w + \frac{g'}{6} \sin \theta_w \right) d_l^\dagger \tilde{\tau}_\mu Z_\mu d_l + \frac{g}{\sqrt{2}} \left(u_l^\dagger \tilde{\tau}_\mu W_\mu^+ d_l + d_l^\dagger \tilde{\tau}_\mu W_\mu^- u_l \right) - \frac{e}{3} d_l^\dagger \tilde{\tau}_\mu A_\mu d_l - \frac{1}{3} g' \cos \theta_w d_r^\dagger \tau_\mu A_\mu d_r + \frac{1}{3} g' \sin \theta_w d_r^\dagger \tau_\mu Z_\mu d_r. \quad (2.32)$$

The complete Lagrangian of the modified Electroweak Model is given by the sum $L_{EWM}(\epsilon) = L_B(\epsilon) + L_L(\epsilon) + L_Q(\epsilon)$ and takes the form

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{L}_{EWM}(\epsilon) &= L(\epsilon) + L^{int}(\epsilon) \\ &= L_0 + \epsilon^2 L_2 + L_0^{int} + \epsilon^2 L_2^{int} + \epsilon^4 L_4. \end{aligned} \quad (2.33)$$

where

$$L_0 = L_{B,0} + L_{L,0} + L_{Q,0},$$

$$L_0^{int} = L_{B,0}^{int} + L_{L,0}^{int} + L_{Q,0}^{int},$$

$$L_2 = L_{B,2} + L_{L,2} + L_{Q,2},$$

$$L_2^{int} = L_{B,2}^{int} + L_{L,2}^{int} + L_{Q,2}^{int}, \quad L_4^{int} = L_{B,4}^{int}. \quad (2.34)$$

We assume that the contraction parameter is monotonous function $\epsilon(T) = AT^{-q}$, $q > 0$ of the temperature (or average energy) of the Universe with the property $\epsilon(T) \rightarrow 0$ for $T \rightarrow \infty$. When $\epsilon \rightarrow 0$, the terms with higher powers of ϵ make a smaller contribution as compared to the terms with lower powers. Thus, the Electroweak Model demonstrates three stages behavior when moving back in time to the moment of the creation of the Universe, which differ in degrees of the contraction parameter.

According to modern knowledge about the world of particles, leptons and quarks form three generations. The next two lepton generations are introduced in a similar way. They are left $SU(2)$ -doublets

$$\begin{pmatrix} \nu_\mu \\ \mu \end{pmatrix}_l, \quad \begin{pmatrix} \nu_\tau \\ \tau \end{pmatrix}_l, \quad Y = -\frac{1}{2} \quad (2.35)$$

and right $SU(2)$ -singlets: $\mu_r, \tau_r, Y = -1$. The next generations of quarks (c, s) and (t, b) are described by left fields

$$\begin{pmatrix} c_l \\ s_l \end{pmatrix}, \quad \begin{pmatrix} t_l \\ b_l \end{pmatrix}, \quad Y = \frac{1}{6} \quad (2.36)$$

which are $SU(2)$ -doublets while right fields are $SU(2)$ -singlets: $c_r, t_r, Y = \frac{2}{3}$; $s_r, b_r, Y = -\frac{1}{3}$. Lagrangians of the next generations of quarks are defined similarly to (2.26). The complete Lagrangians of all generations of quarks and leptons are summed over all generations. We will discuss only the first generations.

3. Quantum chromodynamics at high energies

QCD is the theory of strong interactions of quarks. It is a gauge theory based on the group $SU(3)$, which acts in the space \mathbf{C}_3 of the color quark states $q = \begin{pmatrix} q_1 \\ q_2 \\ q_3 \end{pmatrix} \equiv \begin{pmatrix} q_R \\ q_G \\ q_B \end{pmatrix} \in$

\mathbf{C}_3 [1]. Here $q(x)$ denotes the quark fields $q = u, d, s, c, b, t$ and R (red), G (green), B (blue) are color degrees of freedom. The $SU(3)$ gauge bosons are called gluons. There are eight gluons in total, which are the force carrier between quarks. The QCD Lagrangian is taken in the form

$$\mathcal{L} = \sum_q (\bar{q}^i (i\gamma^\mu) (D_\mu)_{ij} q^j - m_q \bar{q}^i q_i) - \frac{1}{4} \sum_{\alpha=1}^8 F_{\mu\nu}^\alpha F^{\mu\nu\alpha}, \quad (3.1)$$

where $D_\mu q$ are the following covariant derivatives:

$$D_\mu q = \left(\partial_\mu - ig_s \left(\frac{\lambda^\alpha}{2} \right) A_\mu^\alpha \right) q, \quad (3.2)$$

g_s is the strong coupling constant, $t^a = \lambda^a/2$ are the generators of $SU(3)$, λ^a are Gell-Mann matrices in the form

$$\lambda^1 = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix}, \quad \lambda^2 = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & -i & 0 \\ i & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix},$$

$$\lambda^3 = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & -1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix}, \quad \lambda^4 = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 1 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix},$$

$$\lambda^5 = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & -i \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \\ i & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix}, \quad \lambda^6 = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 \end{pmatrix},$$

$$\lambda^7 = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & -i \\ 0 & i & 0 \end{pmatrix}, \quad \lambda^8 = \frac{1}{\sqrt{3}} \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & -2 \end{pmatrix}. \quad (3.3)$$

Gluon stress tensor is defined by the equation

$$F_{\mu\nu}^\alpha = \partial_\mu A_\nu^\alpha - \partial_\nu A_\mu^\alpha + g_s f^{\alpha\beta\gamma} A_\mu^\beta A_\nu^\gamma. \quad (3.4)$$

Here $f^{\alpha\beta\gamma}$ are the structure constant of the algebra $su(3)$: $[t^\alpha, t^\beta] = i f^{\alpha\beta\gamma} t^\gamma$, $\alpha, \beta, \gamma =$

$1, \dots, 8$. They are antisymmetric on all indices and its nonzero values are as follows:

$$f^{123} = 1, \quad f^{147} = f^{246} = f^{257} = f^{345} = \frac{1}{2},$$

$$f^{156} = f^{367} = -\frac{1}{2}, \quad f^{458} = f^{678} = \frac{\sqrt{3}}{2}. \quad (3.5)$$

Further, we will consider only two types of quarks $q = u, d$ and take into account the field transformations that follow from the Electroweak Model. The contracted group $SU(3; \epsilon)$ is defined by the action

$$q'(\epsilon) = U(\epsilon)q(\epsilon),$$

$$\begin{pmatrix} q'_1 \\ \epsilon q'_2 \\ \epsilon^2 q'_3 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} u_{11} & \epsilon u_{12} & \epsilon^2 u_{13} \\ \epsilon u_{21} & u_{22} & \epsilon u_{23} \\ \epsilon^2 u_{31} & \epsilon u_{32} & u_{33} \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} q_1 \\ \epsilon q_2 \\ \epsilon^2 q_3 \end{pmatrix} \quad (3.6)$$

in the color space $\mathbf{C}_3(\epsilon)$ for $\epsilon \rightarrow 0$, where $q_1 = u_1, \epsilon d_1$, $q_2 = u_2, \epsilon d_2$, $q_3 = u_3, \epsilon d_3$. Under this action the Hermitian forms

$$u^\dagger(\epsilon)u(\epsilon) = |u_1|^2 + \epsilon^2 |u_2|^2 + \epsilon^4 |u_3|^2,$$

$$d^\dagger(\epsilon)d(\epsilon) = |d_1|^2 + \epsilon^2 |d_2|^2 + \epsilon^4 |d_3|^2. \quad (3.7)$$

remain invariant.

Passage from the classical group $SU(3)$ and the space \mathbf{C}_3 to the group $SU(3; \epsilon)$ and the space $\mathbf{C}_3(\epsilon)$ is carried out by transforming the gauge fields A_μ^α (3.2) and colors of component quarks of the form

$$u_1 \rightarrow u_1, \quad u_2 \rightarrow \epsilon u_2, \quad u_3 \rightarrow \epsilon^2 u_3,$$

$$d_1 \rightarrow \epsilon d_1, \quad d_2 \rightarrow \epsilon^2 d_2, \quad d_3 \rightarrow \epsilon^3 d_3,$$

$$A_\mu^m \rightarrow \epsilon A_\mu^m, \quad m = 1, 2, 6, 7, \quad A_\mu^{4,5} \rightarrow \epsilon^2 A_\mu^{4,5}. \quad (3.8)$$

In this case, the diagonal gauge fields A_μ^3, A_μ^8 do not change. These substitutions lead to the following expansion of the quark part of the

QCD Lagrangian in powers of the contraction parameter

$$L_{u,4} = i\bar{u}_3\gamma^\mu\partial_\mu u_3 - m_u |u_3|^2, \quad (3.15)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{L}_q(\epsilon) &= L_q(\epsilon) + L_q^{int}(\epsilon) \\ &= \sum_{k=0}^3 \epsilon^{2k} (L_{q,2k} + L_{q,2k}^{int}), \end{aligned} \quad (3.9)$$

$$L_{u,4}^{int} = \frac{g_s}{2} \left[-\frac{2}{\sqrt{3}} |u_3|^2 \gamma^\mu A_\mu^8 \right.$$

where

$$L_{q,0} = L_{u,0}, \quad L_{q,2} = L_{u,2} + L_{d,0}, \quad +u_1\bar{u}_3\gamma^\mu (A_\mu^4 + iA_\mu^5) + \bar{u}_1u_3\gamma^\mu (A_\mu^4 - iA_\mu^5)$$

$$L_{q,4} = L_{u,4} + L_{d,2}, \quad L_{q,6} = L_{d,4}. \quad (3.10)$$

Here

$$L_{u,0} = i\bar{u}_1\gamma^\mu\partial_\mu u_1 - m_u |u_1|^2, \quad (3.11)$$

$$\left. +u_2\bar{u}_3\gamma^\mu (A_\mu^6 + iA_\mu^7) + \bar{u}_2u_3\gamma^\mu (A_\mu^6 - iA_\mu^7) \right]. \quad (3.16)$$

$$L_{u,0}^{int} = +\frac{g_s}{2} |u_1|^2 \gamma^\mu \left(\frac{1}{\sqrt{3}} A_\mu^8 + A_\mu^3 \right), \quad (3.12)$$

The terms $L_{d,2k}$, $L_{d,2k}^{int}$, $k = 0, 1, 2$ are described by the formulas (3.12)–(3.16) with u_p replaced by d_p , $p = 1, 2, 3$.

$$L_{u,2} = i\bar{u}_2\gamma^\mu\partial_\mu u_2 - m_u |u_2|^2, \quad (3.13)$$

The gluon part $L_{gl} = -\frac{1}{4}F_{\mu\nu}^\alpha F^{\mu\nu\alpha}$ of the Lagrangian becomes

$$L_{u,2}^{int} = \frac{g_s}{2} \left[|u_2|^2 \gamma^\mu \left(\frac{1}{\sqrt{3}} A_\mu^8 - A_\mu^3 \right) \right.$$

$$\left. \mathcal{L}_{gl}(\epsilon) = L_{gl}^{(0)} + \epsilon^2 L_{gl}^{(2)} + \epsilon^4 L_{gl}^{(4)} + \epsilon^6 L_{gl}^{(6)} + \epsilon^8 L_{gl}^{(8)}, \right. \quad (3.17)$$

where

$$\left. +u_1\bar{u}_2\gamma^\mu (A_\mu^1 + iA_\mu^2) + \bar{u}_1u_2\gamma^\mu (A_\mu^1 - iA_\mu^2) \right], \quad (3.14)$$

$$L_{gl}^{(0)} = -\frac{1}{4} \left\{ (\partial_\mu A_\nu^3 - \partial_\nu A_\mu^3)^2 + (\partial_\mu A_\nu^8 - \partial_\nu A_\mu^8)^2 \right\}, \quad (3.18)$$

$$\begin{aligned} L_{gl}^{(2)} &= -\frac{1}{4} \left\{ \left(\partial_\mu A_\nu^1 - \partial_\nu A_\mu^1 + g_s (A_\mu^2 A_\nu^3 - A_\mu^3 A_\nu^2) \right)^2 \right. \\ &+ \left(\partial_\mu A_\nu^6 - \partial_\nu A_\mu^6 + \frac{g_s}{2} [(A_\mu^3 A_\nu^7 - A_\mu^7 A_\nu^3) + \sqrt{3} (A_\mu^7 A_\nu^8 - A_\mu^8 A_\nu^7)] \right)^2 \\ &\left. + \left(\partial_\mu A_\nu^2 - \partial_\nu A_\mu^2 - g_s (A_\mu^1 A_\nu^3 - A_\mu^3 A_\nu^1) \right)^2 + \left(\partial_\mu A_\nu^7 - \partial_\nu A_\mu^7 - \frac{g_s}{2} [A_\mu^3 A_\nu^6 - A_\mu^6 A_\nu^3] \right)^2 \right\} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& +\sqrt{3} (A_\mu^6 A_\nu^8 - A_\mu^8 A_\nu^6) \Big]^2 + g_s \left[\left(2 (A_\mu^1 A_\nu^2 - A_\mu^2 A_\nu^1) \right. \right. \\
& \left. \left. - A_\mu^6 A_\nu^7 + A_\mu^7 A_\nu^6 \right) (\partial_\mu A_\nu^3 - \partial_\nu A_\mu^3) + \sqrt{3} (A_\mu^6 A_\nu^7 - A_\mu^7 A_\nu^6) (\partial_\mu A_\nu^8 - \partial_\nu A_\mu^8) \right] \Big\}, \quad (3.19)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
L_{gl}^{(4)} = & -\frac{1}{4} \left\{ (\partial_\mu A_\nu^4 - \partial_\nu A_\mu^4)^2 + (\partial_\mu A_\nu^5 - \partial_\nu A_\mu^5)^2 + g_s \left[\left(A_\mu^4 A_\nu^7 - A_\mu^7 A_\nu^4 - A_\mu^5 A_\nu^6 + A_\mu^6 A_\nu^5 \right) (\partial_\mu A_\nu^1 - \partial_\nu A_\mu^1) \right. \right. \\
& + \left(A_\mu^4 A_\nu^6 - A_\mu^6 A_\nu^4 + A_\mu^5 A_\nu^7 - A_\mu^7 A_\nu^5 \right) (\partial_\mu A_\nu^2 - \partial_\nu A_\mu^2) - \left(A_\mu^1 A_\nu^7 - A_\mu^7 A_\nu^1 + A_\mu^2 A_\nu^6 - A_\mu^6 A_\nu^2 + A_\mu^3 A_\nu^5 - A_\mu^5 A_\nu^3 \right. \\
& \left. - \sqrt{3} (A_\mu^5 A_\nu^8 - A_\mu^8 A_\nu^5) \right) (\partial_\mu A_\nu^4 - \partial_\nu A_\mu^4) + \left(A_\mu^1 A_\nu^6 - A_\mu^6 A_\nu^1 - A_\mu^2 A_\nu^7 + A_\mu^7 A_\nu^2 + A_\mu^3 A_\nu^4 - A_\mu^4 A_\nu^3 \right. \\
& \left. - \sqrt{3} (A_\mu^4 A_\nu^8 - A_\mu^8 A_\nu^4) \right) (\partial_\mu A_\nu^5 - \partial_\nu A_\mu^5) + \left(A_\mu^2 A_\nu^4 - A_\mu^4 A_\nu^2 - A_\mu^1 A_\nu^5 + A_\mu^5 A_\nu^1 \right) (\partial_\mu A_\nu^6 - \partial_\nu A_\mu^6) \\
& \left. + \left(A_\mu^1 A_\nu^4 - A_\mu^4 A_\nu^1 + A_\mu^2 A_\nu^5 - A_\mu^5 A_\nu^2 \right) (\partial_\mu A_\nu^7 - \partial_\nu A_\mu^7) + \sqrt{3} (A_\mu^4 A_\nu^5 - A_\mu^5 A_\nu^4) (\partial_\mu A_\nu^8 - \partial_\nu A_\mu^8) \right] \\
& + g_s^2 \left[\left(A_\mu^1 A_\nu^2 - A_\mu^2 A_\nu^1 \right)^2 + \left(A_\mu^6 A_\nu^7 - A_\mu^7 A_\nu^6 \right)^2 - \left(A_\mu^1 A_\nu^2 - A_\mu^2 A_\nu^1 \right) \left(A_\mu^6 A_\nu^7 - A_\mu^7 A_\nu^6 \right) \right. \\
& - \left(A_\mu^1 A_\nu^3 - A_\mu^3 A_\nu^1 \right) \left(A_\mu^4 A_\nu^6 - A_\mu^6 A_\nu^4 A_\mu^5 A_\nu^7 - A_\mu^7 A_\nu^5 \right) + \left(A_\mu^2 A_\nu^3 - A_\mu^3 A_\nu^2 \right) \left(A_\mu^4 A_\nu^7 - A_\mu^7 A_\nu^4 - A_\mu^5 A_\nu^6 + A_\mu^6 A_\nu^5 \right) \\
& + \frac{1}{2} \left(A_\mu^3 A_\nu^7 - A_\mu^7 A_\nu^3 + \sqrt{3} (A_\mu^7 A_\nu^8 - A_\mu^8 A_\nu^7) \right) \left(A_\mu^2 A_\nu^4 - A_\mu^4 A_\nu^2 - A_\mu^1 A_\nu^5 + A_\mu^5 A_\nu^1 \right) \\
& - \frac{1}{2} \left(A_\mu^3 A_\nu^6 - A_\mu^6 A_\nu^3 + \sqrt{3} (A_\mu^6 A_\nu^8 - A_\mu^8 A_\nu^6) \right) \left(A_\mu^1 A_\nu^4 - A_\mu^4 A_\nu^1 + A_\mu^2 A_\nu^5 - A_\mu^5 A_\nu^2 \right) \\
& + \frac{1}{2} \left(A_\mu^1 A_\nu^7 - A_\mu^7 A_\nu^1 + A_\mu^2 A_\nu^6 - A_\mu^6 A_\nu^2 \right. \\
& \left. + A_\mu^3 A_\nu^5 - A_\mu^5 A_\nu^3 - \sqrt{3} (A_\mu^5 A_\nu^8 - A_\mu^8 A_\nu^5) \right)^2 + \frac{1}{2} \left(A_\mu^1 A_\nu^6 - A_\mu^6 A_\nu^1 - A_\mu^2 A_\nu^7 + A_\mu^7 A_\nu^2 \right. \\
& \left. \left. + A_\mu^3 A_\nu^4 - A_\mu^4 A_\nu^3 - \sqrt{3} (A_\mu^4 A_\nu^8 - A_\mu^8 A_\nu^4) \right)^2 \right] \Big\}, \quad (3.20)
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 L_{gl}^{(6)} = & -\frac{g_s^2}{16} \left\{ \left(A_\mu^4 A_\nu^7 - A_\mu^7 A_\nu^4 - A_\mu^5 A_\nu^6 + A_\mu^6 A_\nu^5 \right)^2 + \left(A_\mu^4 A_\nu^6 - A_\mu^6 A_\nu^4 + A_\mu^5 A_\nu^7 - A_\mu^7 A_\nu^5 \right)^2 \right. \\
 & + \left(A_\mu^2 A_\nu^4 - A_\mu^4 A_\nu^2 - A_\mu^1 A_\nu^5 + A_\mu^5 A_\nu^1 \right)^2 + \left(A_\mu^1 A_\nu^4 - A_\mu^4 A_\nu^1 + A_\mu^2 A_\nu^5 - A_\mu^5 A_\nu^2 \right)^2 \\
 & \left. + 4 \left(A_\mu^1 A_\nu^2 - A_\mu^2 A_\nu^1 + A_\mu^6 A_\nu^7 - A_\mu^7 A_\nu^6 \right) \left(A_\mu^4 A_\nu^5 - A_\mu^5 A_\nu^4 \right) \right\}, \tag{3.21}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$L_{gl}^{(8)} = -\frac{g_s^2}{4} \left(A_\mu^4 A_\nu^5 - A_\mu^5 A_\nu^4 \right)^2. \tag{3.22}$$

As a result of combining (3.9) and (3.17), the modified QCD Lagrangian can be represented as an expansion in powers of the contraction parameter

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathcal{L}_{QCD}(\epsilon) &= L_q(\epsilon) + L_q^{int}(\epsilon) + \mathcal{L}_{gl}(\epsilon) \\
 &= \mathcal{L}^{(0)} + \epsilon^2 \mathcal{L}^{(2)} + \epsilon^4 \mathcal{L}^{(4)} + \epsilon^6 \mathcal{L}^{(6)} + \epsilon^8 \mathcal{L}^{(8)}, \tag{3.23}
 \end{aligned}$$

where

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathcal{L}^{(0)} &= L_{u,0} + L_{u,0}^{int} + L_{gl}^{(0)}, \quad \mathcal{L}^{(8)} = L_{gl}^{(8)}, \\
 \mathcal{L}^{(2p)} &= L_{u,2p} + L_{d,2(p-1)} + L_{u,2p}^{int} + L_{d,2(p-1)}^{int} \\
 &\quad + L_{gl}^{(2p)}, \quad p = 1, 2, 3. \tag{3.24}
 \end{aligned}$$

According to our hypothesis, the contraction parameter is a monotonic function of temperature $\epsilon \rightarrow 0$ for $T \rightarrow \infty$. According to the modern concept of the origin of the Universe [8], very high (“infinite”) temperatures may exist in the first stages of the Big Bang immediately after inflation in the pre-electroweak epoch.

4. Estimation of boundaries between epochs in the evolution of the Universe

Combining the Lagrangians of the electroweak model (2.33) and quantum

chromodynamics (3.23), we obtain the Lagrangian of the standard model, represented as an expansion in powers of the contraction parameter

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathcal{L}_{SM}(\epsilon) &= L_{EWM}(\epsilon) + \mathcal{L}_{QCD}(\epsilon) \\
 &= L(\epsilon) + L_q(\epsilon) + L^{int}(\epsilon) + L_q^{int}(\epsilon) + \mathcal{L}_{gl}(\epsilon) \\
 &= \mathcal{L}_0 + \epsilon^2 \mathcal{L}_2 + \epsilon^4 \mathcal{L}_4 + \epsilon^6 \mathcal{L}_6 + \epsilon^8 \mathcal{L}_8, \tag{4.1}
 \end{aligned}$$

where, taking into account the expressions (2.34) and (3.24), we have

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathcal{L}_p &= L_p + L_p^{int} + \mathcal{L}^{(p)}, \quad p = 0, 2, 4, \\
 \mathcal{L}_6 &= \mathcal{L}^{(6)}, \quad \mathcal{L}_8 = \mathcal{L}^{(8)}. \tag{4.2}
 \end{aligned}$$

Thus, depending on the degree of the contraction parameter The Standard Model exhibits five stages of behavior as it moves back in time to the time the universe was born. As noted, the contraction of the gauge group makes it possible to order in time different stages of its development, but does not allow determining their absolute dates. Additional assumptions needed. We assume that the contraction parameters for QCD and the Electroweak Model are the same.

Further, we assume that the electroweak model, whose Lagrangian includes minimal terms proportional to ϵ^4 , restored in the standard form at its characteristic temperature $T_4 = 100$ GeV,

while the complete reconstruction of QCD, with minimal terms in the Lagrangian of the order of ϵ^8 , occurs at a temperature $T_8 = 0.2 \text{ GeV}$.

Denote by Δ the cutoff level for ϵ^k , $k = 2, 4, 6, 8$, i.e. for $\epsilon^k < \Delta$ all terms in the Lagrangian are proportional to ϵ^k are assumed to be negligible. Finally, we assume that the contraction parameter depends on the temperature

$$\epsilon(T) = \left(\frac{A}{T}\right)^q, \quad q > 0, \quad (4.3)$$

where A is a constant of dimension T . From the equation for QCD $\epsilon^8(T_8) = (AT_8^{-1})^{8q} = \Delta$ we get $A = T_8 \Delta^{1/8q} = 0,2 \Delta^{1/8q} \text{ GeV}$. From a similar equation for the electroweak model, we find the cutoff level $\Delta = (T_8 T_4^{-1})^{8q} = (0.2 \cdot 10^{-2})^{8q} \approx 10^{-22q}$, as well as the dimensional constant $A = T_8^2 T_4^{-1} = 4 \cdot 10^{-4} \text{ GeV}$. Using the equation for the k th power $\epsilon^k(T_k) = (AT_k^{-1})^{qk} = \Delta$, we have

$$T_k = T_8 \left(\frac{T_8}{T_4}\right)^{1-\frac{8}{k}} \quad (4.4)$$

and easily find the boundary values (GeV):

$$T_2 = 10^7, \quad T_4 = 10^2, \quad T_6 = 1, \quad T_8 = 2 \cdot 10^{-1}, \quad (4.5)$$

which do not depend on the degree q relating the contraction parameter and the temperature (4.3), but the cutoff parameter depends on q . Estimation of “infinite” temperature $T_2 \approx 10^7 \text{ GeV}$ much less Planck energy $\approx 10^{19} \text{ GeV}$, at which the effect of gravity becomes significant. Thus, the obtained evolution of elementary particles does not go beyond the limits of problems described by electroweak and strong interactions.

5. Temperature dependence of the Higgs boson production cross section

Feynman diagram describing the dominant mechanism for the production and detection of Higgs bosons in experiments at the Large Hadron Collider (LHC), after transforming the

fields of gauge bosons (2.7), fields of leptons (2.20) and quarks (3.8), takes the form shown in Fig. 1, where L denotes a pair of electrons or muons [11]. Counting the contraction factors

FIG. 1. Modified diagram of Higgs boson production in a four-lepton process.

on the right side of the diagram gives ϵ^4 . This factor takes into account the contribution of electroweak interactions to the mechanism under consideration. The rest of the diagram can be represented as a loop of virtual quarks (Fig. 2) depending only on strong interactions.

FIG. 2. Higgs boson production diagram dependent on strong quark interactions. The following notation are used: $\alpha = 1$ for the t -quark and $\alpha = 2$ for the b -quark.

As a result of the contraction of the QCD gauge group there is a “splitting” of the processes of formation of Higgs bosons during the interaction of quarks into different channels associated with different dependence of the colors (components) of quarks and gluons on ϵ . The amplitudes M_{ik} of the Higgs boson production processes are multiplied by the contraction parameter to varying degrees, depending on which color components of the virtual quarks

are involved in its formation. The cross section of the process is proportional to the square of the amplitude $\sigma_{ik} = |M_{ik}|^2$. Due to the smallness of the parameter $\epsilon = (AT^{-1})^q, q > 0$ main contribution to the total cross section as T increases, they give channels proportional to contraction parameter with negative powers. Maximum deposit introduces the $M_{31}(\epsilon)$ channel (Fig. 3) involving the first and third t -quark components

$$\sigma_t(T) = T^{8q} \sigma_t^{in}, \quad (5.1)$$

where σ_t^{in} is the untransformed section for $\epsilon = 1$.

FIG. 3. A loop of virtual quarks with components q_1, q_3 and an antiquark with component \bar{q}_3 ; a channel amplitude is called $M_{31}(\epsilon)$.

The results of measurements of the cross section for the production of Higgs bosons in four-lepton decay, obtained at the LHC over a number of years in the collision of proton beams of different energies, are given in the review [12]: $\sigma_{tot} = 17$ for $E = 7$, $\sigma_{tot} = 22$ for $E = 8$, $\sigma_{tot} = 56$ for $E = 13$, $\sigma_{tot} = 57$ for $E = 14$. Here E is given in TeV, and σ_{tot} is given in picobarns. It follows from these data that the measured cross sections demonstrates the quadratic dependence on the energy of $\sigma_{tot} \sim E^2$. It is logical to assume that the temperature T of the Universe and the collision energy E of proton beams in the LHC are proportional to each other $T \sim E$, then $\sigma_{tot} \sim T^2$.

Cross section (5.1) for the t -quark production channel with amplitude $M_{31}(\epsilon)$ has a quadratic dependence $\sigma_t(T) \sim T^2$ for $q = \frac{1}{4}$. Other growing cross sections are proportional to T (the same channel $M_{31}(\epsilon)$ for the b quark and channel $M_{32}(\epsilon)$ for the t quark). The question of

the ratio of the contributions of these and other processes to the total cross section σ_{tot} remains open. The experimental cross sections σ_{tot} for the production of Higgs bosons contain contributions from both t - and b -quarks, as well as from all their colors (components). Therefore, this data cannot be used directly for direct comparison with theoretical values. Additional assumptions are needed about the share of t - and b -loop contributions in general, on the contributions of each color component of quarks to the total cross section, and others. Nevertheless, it can be argued that **the hypothesis of contraction of the gauge group of the Standard Model does not contradict the available experimental data on the cross sections for the production of Higgs bosons.**

6. Development of particles and interactions in the process of evolution

The expansion (4.1) of the Standard Model Lagrangian in powers of the contraction parameter opens up the possibility of constructing intermediate limit models with different particles and interactions between them. We can take the Lagrangian \mathcal{L}_0 as the original limit system for $T > 10^7$ GeV, then add \mathcal{L}_2 and get the second limit model with Lagrangian $\mathcal{L}_{SM}^{(2)} = \mathcal{L}_0 + \mathcal{L}_2$ for 10^7 GeV $> T > 10^2$ GeV. After that, you can add \mathcal{L}_4 and get the following limit model $\mathcal{L}_{SM}^{(4)} = \mathcal{L}_0 + \mathcal{L}_2 + \mathcal{L}_4$ for 10^2 GeV $> T > 1$ GeV and so on until the Lagrangian of the Standard Model is completely restored for $T < 2 \cdot 10^{-1}$ GeV. As we move from one epoch to another, the significant terms in the Lagrangians change, which allows us to draw some conclusions about the particles at different stages of the evolution of the Universe already at the level of classical fields.

In the limit of “infinite” temperature ($\epsilon = 0$, $T > 10^7$ GeV) we obtain the Lagrangian \mathcal{L}_0 of the Standard Model whose quadratic terms contain: massless neutrino and photon, massive Z -boson and Higgs boson (2.13), (2.22), massive monochromatic u -quark (2.29) with the first (R)

component (3.11), (3.12). Higher order terms describe the self-action of the Higgs boson and its interaction with the Z boson (2.15), weak and electromagnetic interactions of neutrino and u -quark with photon and Z -boson (2.23), (2.30), as well as interactions of diagonal gluons (3.18). Note that the charged boson fields W_μ^\pm corresponding to the translation subgroup do not enter the limit Lagrangian \mathcal{L}_0 .

From the explicit expression of the interaction Lagrangian it follows that particles of different sorts do not interact with each other. Only particles of the same type interact, for example, neutrinos interact with each other through neutral currents. All other particles are charged and interact through the exchange of Z bosons and photons. All other particles are charged and interact through the exchange of Z bosons and photons. It looks like some kind of stratification of the Electroweak Model with particles of the same type in each layer.

For $T > 10^7$ GeV, only two components of the gluon field strength tensor remain nonzero

$$F_{\mu\nu}^3 = \partial_\mu A_\nu^3 - \partial_\nu A_\mu^3 = \frac{1}{2} (F_{\mu\nu}^{RR} - F_{\mu\nu}^{GG}),$$

$$F_{\mu\nu}^8 = \partial_\mu A_\nu^8 - \partial_\nu A_\mu^8 = \frac{\sqrt{3}}{2} (F_{\mu\nu}^{RR} + F_{\mu\nu}^{GG}). \quad (6.1)$$

So, using (3.11), (3.12), (3.18), one can write out the limiting QCD Lagrangian in explicit form

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{L}^{(0)} &= L_{u,0} + L_{u,0}^{int} + L_{gl}^{(0)} = \\ &= i\bar{u}_R \gamma^\mu \partial_\mu u_R + \frac{g_s}{2} |u_R|^2 \gamma^\mu A_\mu^{RR} \\ &\quad - \frac{1}{4} (F_{\mu\nu}^{RR})^2 - \frac{1}{4} (F_{\mu\nu}^{GG})^2 - \frac{1}{4} F_{\mu\nu}^{RR} F_{\mu\nu}^{GG}. \end{aligned} \quad (6.2)$$

Hence we conclude that in this limit only dynamic terms survive for one color component of the u -quark, i.e. quarks become monochromatic. The terms describing the interaction of this component with R -gluons also remain nonzero. In addition to R -gluons, there are G -gluons that do

not interact with u_R . Thus, stratification is also present in the QCD sector.

At temperatures 10^7 GeV $\geq T > 10^2$ GeV part \mathcal{L}_2 is added to the Lagrangian, which contains the kinetic terms W^\pm of gauge bosons (2.14), electrons (2.24) and d quarks (2.31), and also describes weak interactions W^\pm with other gauge bosons (2.16) and the Higgs boson. Interactions of a neutrino with an electron (2.25) and between u - and d -quarks (2.32) appear. u -quarks acquire a second color degree of freedom (3.13), which interacts with the first one (3.14). The d -quark has its first color degree of freedom activated. The main part of the electroweak and a significant part of the color interactions are restored in this epoch.

Upon further cooling to temperatures 10^2 GeV $\geq T > 1$ GeV the term \mathcal{L}_4 is added to the Lagrangian, which ensures weak interactions of gauge bosons with each other (2.17). All color components of u -quarks (3.15) and interactions between them (3.16) are restored. The d -quark has a second color degree of freedom, which strongly interacts with the first. A large number of interactions between gluons are activated (3.20).

In the temperature range 1 GeV $\geq T > 0.2$ GeV, the third color degree of freedom of the d -quark appears (3.15), all color interactions are present except for (3.22). Finally, at $T \leq 0.2$ GeV the standard model is fully restored.

7. Conclusions

Based on the observation of the characteristic temperatures of the QCD and the Electroweak Model, i.e. theories that are part of the Standard Model, we have proposed a new paradigm in particle physics. Our hypothesis is that as the temperature of the Universe increases, the Standard Model's gauge group becomes simpler. We believe that the simplification of the gauge group occurs due to its contraction, the parameter of which decreases with increasing temperature of the Universe.

The limiting case of the Standard Model

corresponding to the contraction of its gauge group is considered. The limiting formally “infinite” temperature does not exceed the Planck energy 10^{19} GeV, i.e. particle evolution does not go beyond the problems described by electroweak and strong interactions. The stages of development of the standard model in the process of evolution of the Universe as it cools are described. They differ in degrees of contraction parameter. The intermediate Lagrangians \mathcal{L}_k are found using the Δ cutoff level, taking into account typical QCD energies and the electroweak model. Their explicit form for each stage of development of the Standard Model was obtained from the expansions (2.33),(3.23),(4.1) of the total Lagrangians, which allows us to draw conclusions about the development of interactions and properties of particles in each of the considered epochs.

The resulting scheme of particle evolution does not contradict the history of the Universe

developed from other considerations [1, 8], according to which QCD-induced phase transitions occur later than electroweak phase transitions. In addition, it provides a basis for a more detailed analysis of the stages in the formation of leptons and quark-gluon plasma, taking into account the fact that the terms $L_{gl}^{(6)}$ (3.21) and $L_{gl}^{(8)}$ (3.22) in the gluon Lagrangian L_{gl} (3.17) are negligible at temperatures from 0.2 GeV to 100 GeV.

On the other hand, in contrast to GUT, the presence of a continuously changing parameter makes it possible to analyze the available experimental data in terms of their dependence on temperature. In particular, the experimental data obtained at the Large Hadron Collider on the cross sections for the production of Higgs bosons at energies of 7, 8, 13, and 14 TeV do not contradict the proposed hypothesis.

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